

Supplement to the DFG-Project report “Individual and classroom level factors shaping the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on learning in mathematics“ („Individuelle und schulische Determinanten für die Auswirkungen der COVID-19-Pandemie auf das Lernen in Mathematik“)

Authors: Johannes Hartig & Marit Kristine List, DIPF | Leibniz Institute for Research and Information in Education, Frankfurt/ Main, Germany

Individual and classroom level factors shaping the impact of the
COVID-19 pandemic on learning in mathematics

Summary

As a measure to contain the COVID 19 pandemic, regular face-to-face teaching in schools was suspended for longer periods in the 19/20 and 20/21 school years. The distance learning introduced unfamiliar challenges for schools, students and parents. Moreover, during this period, students' learning was impaired due to higher demands on self-directed learning. Nevertheless, researchers have asserted that high teaching quality may help for compensating negative consequences of the pandemic. Taken together, this draws attention to potentially still-increasing detrimental effects of educational inequality during the pandemic and to the question of how to counter these developments.

The aim of this project was to investigate the mid-term effects of the pandemic-related teaching restrictions in the 20/21 school year on learning success in the 21/22 school year. The project made use of data collected in another project to assess learning progress in mathematics in eighth grade in Hessian grammar schools (Gymnasien). Pandemic-related factors on classroom and individual level assessed retrospectively were used to investigate different pathways of the effects of teaching restrictions on learning progress. Therefore, the project provides beneficial insights on the pandemic's effects on post-pandemic learning.

Objectives

Our research objectives were

- Most important *main effects* to be estimated were those of the pandemic-related factors on classroom and individual levels. Note that student achievement at T1 is targeting learning outcomes in linear equations and linear functions which are not subject matters from the school years affected by the pandemic. Therefore, we assumed effects of pandemic-related factors on student achievement at T2 to be only partially mediated by student achievement at T1.
- The most interesting *indirect effect* was the one of stable socio-economic background (SES) factors on student achievement mediated by individual pandemic-related factors. We expected social inequalities to be mediated substantially, albeit not completely, by those factors.
- *Interactions* to be investigated included the amplification or reduction of classroom level effects by individual factors at home (interaction (a) in Figure 1) and the moderation of pandemic-related effects by teaching quality in the following school year (interactions (b) and (c) in Figure 1).

Figure 1 Schematic illustration of the variables collected and the most important pathways to be investigated.

Note: For this report, teaching quality was not analyzed.

Descriptives and intercorrelations

Table 1 Means (M), standard deviations (SD), Minimum, Maximum, and reliability estimates (Cronbach's Alpha, ICCs).

	No.Items	N	M	SD	Min	Max	Reliability	ICC1	ICC2
Math score T2 ^a 30-31		298	0.60	1.35	-5.80	4.24	0.76 ^b	0.12	0.69
Math score T1 ^a 30-31		297	0	1	-4.52	3.31	0.60 ^b	0.10	0.64
Parental educational level 2		258	4.44	0.78	2.00	5.00	---	0.24	0.83
Distance learning 4		301	3.42	0.53	1.00	4.00	0.62 ^c	0.03	0.36
Individual feedback 3		287	3.08	0.70	1.33	4.00	0.64 ^c	0.17	0.76
Reference to external material 3		289	2.54	0.81	1.00	4.00	0.64 ^c	0.40	0.92
Live communication 2		289	3.30	0.77	1.00	4.00	0.23 ^c	0.32	0.88
Conventional communication channels 2		285	1.30	0.60	1.00	4.00	0.50 ^c	0.04	0.41

Note. ^a standardised values; ^b WLE reliability based on total sample of the COINS project, estimated in TAM (Robitzsch, Kiefer, & Wu, 2022); ^c Cronbach's Alpha. ICC2 was calculated using the average cluster size $k = 16.26$ (see Lüdtke et al, 2009, for details on the calculation procedure).

Table 2 Zero-order correlations among all variables.

	Math score T2	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Math score T1 (1)	0.59***						
Parental educational level (2)	0.10	0.13					
		$p = .05$					
Distance learning (3)	0.14**	0.09	0.09				
		$p = .08$					
Individual feedback (4)	0.04	0.04	0.05	0.03			
Reference to external material (5)	-0.23**	-0.27***	0.03	-0.07	0.11		
Live communication (6)	-0.10	-0.05	-0.05	-0.06	0.17	0.18*	
Conventional communication channels (7)	-0.17***	-0.23***	-0.07	-0.12*	0.06	0.22***	0.05

Note. $N = 309$. To account for clustering effects, Mplus option "type is complex" was used. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; p -values for two-sided significance tests. Correlation coefficients without flagging are not significant.

Regression results

Table 3 Results of the multilevel regression analyses

From	To	M1 ^a <i>B</i>	M2 ^a <i>B</i>	M3 ^{a,b} <i>B</i>	M4a ^a <i>B</i>	M4b ^a <i>B</i>	M4c ^a <i>B</i>	M4d ^a <i>B</i>
Math T1	Math T2	0.83***	0.75***	0.81***	0.71***	0.69***	0.70***	0.70***
Educ. level	Math T2	0.04		0.01				
Distance learning	Math T2	0.08		0.09				
Educ. level	Math T1	0.11		0.13				
Distance learning	Math T1	0.09		0.07				
Educ. level	Distance learning	p = .07 .09		0.09				
Educ. level	Math T2	0.10		0.12				
Distance learning	Math T2	p = .09 0.08 p = .09		p = .06 0.05				
Math T1	Math T2		0.87**	0.54***	1.24***	1.51***	1.34***	0.79**
Individual Feedback	Math T2		0.15**	0.11**	0.05			
External material	Math T2		0.06	0.01		0.11		
Live communication	Math T2		0.06	0.02			0.08	
Conv. comm. channels	Math T2		-0.35***	-0.32***				-0.26***
Individual Feedback	Math T1		0.04	0.03	-0.05			
External material	Math T1		-0.15*	-0.19**		-0.20*		
Live communication	Math T1		-0.08	-0.08*			-0.13	
Conv. comm. channels	Math T1		-0.09	-0.09				-0.15 p = .07
Individual Feedback	Math T2		0.03	0.02				
External material	Math T2		-0.13*	-0.10**				
Live communication	Math T2		-0.07	-0.05*				
Conv. comm. channels	Math T2		-0.08	-0.05				
Individual Feedback * distance learning	Math T2				-0.04			
External material * distance learning	Math T2					-0.08 p = .09		
Live communication * distance learning	Math T2						-0.10**	
Conv. comm. channels * distance learning	Math T2							-0.03
Individual Feedback * distance learning	Math T1				0.02			
External material * distance learning	Math T1					-0.09*		
Live communication * distance learning	Math T1						-0.06*	
Conv. comm. channels * distance learning	Math T1							-0.01

Note. *** $p < 0.001$; ** $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$; p-values for two-sided significance tests. Coefficients without flagging are not significant. ^a: Sample sizes for the models are: M1: $N = 258$; M2: N ; M3: $N = 258$; M4a-d: $N = 297$. ^b: variance of achievement at T2 is fixed to 0.